

Studies on the Synthesis of Biheterocycles and their Biological Activities

S. P. HIREMATH^a, H. K. S. SWAMY^a, B. H. M. MRUTHYUNJAYASWAMY^a, S. M. PATIL^b, K. M. K SWAMY^b and S. M. SHANTAKUMAR^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, V. L. College of Pharmacy, Raichur-584 101

Manuscript received 28 June 1993, revised 26 November 1993, accepted 11 January 1994

4-Amino-5-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-3-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazoles (3a-d), 5-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-2-phenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4a-d), 4-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-5-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones (5a-d) and 2-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)imino-3-phenoxyacetamido-5H-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones (6a-d) have been synthesised and screened for their antibacterial, antifungal, oxytocic and catatonic activities.

In view of the biological activities associated with aryloxyacetic acid, aryloxypropionic acid¹, thiosemicarbazides and triazoles, oxadiazoles, 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones and thiazolidinones obtainable therefrom², we planned to synthesise and study the biological activities of the compounds having such functionalities/moieties.

We report here the synthesis of thiosemicarbazides substituted by two biodynamic molecules such as indole and substituted aryloxy-methyl moieties and used them as intermediates to synthesise indole biheterocycles. The starting material (2-phenylindol)-3-ylisothiocyanate³ (1) is condensed with some substituted aryloxyacetic acid hydrazides to get 3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-1-phenoxyacetyl thiosemicarbazides (2a-d). These thiosemicarbazides are used in the synthesis of various biheterocycles as discussed below.

Results and Discussion

(2-Phenylindol)-3-ylisothiocyanate (1) when refluxed with various phenoxyacetic acid hydrazides in dry benzene yielded 3-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-1-substituted-phenoxyacetyl-thiosemicarbazides (2a-d). The conversion of compound 1 to 2a-d was confirmed by the disappearance of isothiocyanate peak of 1 and appearance of carbonyl and amide NH peaks in ir spectra of 2a-d and also amide NH, acetyl CH₂ proton signals of 2a-d in nmr spectra.

Scheme 1

Compounds 2a-d on refluxing with hydrazine hydrate and iodine in potassium iodide solution in alkaline medium gave 4-amino-5-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-3-substituted-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazoles (3a-d) and 5-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-2-substituted-phenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (4a-d) respectively. The process of cyclisation in the formation of amino triazoles (3a-d) was also confirmed by the evolution of H₂S gas, tested by lead acetate paper. Compounds 2a-d on treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide under reflux con-

dition and with monochloroacetic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid yielded 4-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)-5-substituted-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones (**5a-d**) and 2-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)imino-3-substituted-phenoxyacetamido-5H-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones (**6a-d**) respectively).

Antimicrobial activity : All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against various pathogenic bacteria, such as *S. aureus*, *S. citreus*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and against fungi *mucor*, *A. niger* by cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in DMF by using the standards sulphamethoxazole (250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and gentamycin (100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for bacteria and nystatin (500 I.U. ml^{-1}) for fungi respectively. Amongst the compounds tested for the antibacterial activity of **2a,b**, **3d**, **4b,d**, **5a,d** were found higher and other compounds showed good to moderate activity. Compounds **3b-d**, **4c**, **5b** and **6d** exhibited very good inhibition to the growth of both fungi, and rest of the compounds were found moderately active.

Oxytocic activity : Some of the compounds were tested for their oxytocic activity on isolated rat uterus and contractions were recorded on a slow moving kymograph using a frontal lever. Compounds **3a** and **3b** showed complete inhibition of oxytocic activity whereas **4b** and **5b** exhibited moderate and **4a** and **6a** average inhibition.

Catatonic activity : The catatonic activity of compounds **3b**, **5a** and **7c** were studied⁵ on albino rats of either sex using chlorpromazine as the control and the scoring was made at 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, 90 and 120 min. The compounds were found to have non-significant effect when compared with standard drug *Scopolamine*.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 881 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) on a Varian CFT-20 instrument using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental (C, H and N) analyses.

The isothiocyanate (**1**)³ and thiosemicarbazides (**2a-d**) were prepared in 75–80% yields according to the reported methods⁶ starting from 2-phenyl-3-aminoindole : **1** ν_{max} 3 420 (indole NH) and 2 100 cm^{-1} (N=C=S); **2a**, m.p. 276°, ν_{max} 3 420 (indole NH), 3 340, 3 300 (NH/NH), 1 660 (C=O) and 1 240 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ 4.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.4–7.7 (14H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, indole NH), 11.85 (1H, s, $-\text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) and 13.05 (2H, s, $\text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{S}$); **2b**, m.p. 280°, c, 258°, **d**, 270°.

4-Amino-5-(2'-phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-3-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazole (3a) : The thiosemicarbazide (**2a**; 0.003 mol) was refluxed in hydrazine hydrate (99–100%; 10 ml) for 2 h under anhydrous conditions. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice slowly with constant stirring. The solid separated after neutralising with acetic acid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 260°; ν_{max} 3 425 (indole NH), 3 340 and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH/NH₂). Similar treatment of **2b-d** gave **3b-d** having m.p. 283, 250, and 276° respectively.

5-(2'-Phenylindol-3'-yl)amino-2-phenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a) : To a solution of **2a** (0.003 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) and aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.24 mol; 2N) was added iodine in potassium iodide solution (5%) with shaking till the colour of iodine persisted and refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was cooled and acidified with acetic acid (10%). The solid separated was washed with water then with carbon disulphide and crystallised from ethanol, (68%), m.p. 242°; ν_{max} 3 430 (indole NH) and 3 320 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 4.75 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.4–8.05 (14H, m, ArH) and 8.55 (1H, s, indole NH). The compounds **4b-d** were similarly prepared (70%) from **2b-d**, having m.p. 220, 140, and 198° respectively.

4-(2'-Phenylindol-3'-yl)-5-phenoxy-methyl-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione (5a) : A suspension of **2a** (0.003 mol) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (6 ml; 4%) was refluxed slowly for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with dilute acetic acid (10%). The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-benzene, (80%),

m.p. 270°; ν_{\max} 3425 (indole NH), 3330 (NH) and 1245 cm^{-1} (C=S); m/z 398 (M^+), 305, 276, 232 and 193 (for the fragments $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$ -, $\text{N}=\text{NH}$, C=S and HCN lost from the molecular ion sequentially). Compounds **5b-d** had m.p. 268, 250 and 282° respectively.

2-(2'-Phenylindol-3'-yl)imino-3-phenoxyacetamido-5H-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6a**) : A mixture of **2a** (0.003 mol), monochloroacetic acid (0.003 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.0035 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The solid obtained was washed with excess of cold water and crystallised from benzene-ethanol, (85%), m.p. 228°; ν_{\max} 3420 (indole NH), 3260 (NH), 1700 and 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O/C=O); δ 4.0 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.75 (2H, s, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$), 6.4-7.5 (14H, m, ArH), 7.95 (1H, s, indole NH) and 10.7 (1H, s, O=C-NH); m/z 456 (M^+), 390, 305 due to the sequential expulsion of fragments $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and CH_2 lost from the [M^+] and 363 due to the expulsion of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$ from [M^+] directly. Compounds **6b-d** prepared similarly from **2b-d** had m.p. 238, 120 and 118° respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Director, C.D.R.I.,

Lucknow, for analytical and spectral data and also to A.M.E's Pharmacy College management for facilities.

References

1. M. NAKANISHI, S. SAHEKI and A. TSUDA, Jpn. Pat. 7 021 304/1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 66336); R. F. W. RAETZ and M. J. GRUBER, U.S. PAT. 3 598 872/1971 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1971, **75**, 110064); R. H. LEWIS, J. R. HOUSLEY, H. C. RICHARDS, J. S. NICHOLSON, M. W. BAKER and S. S. ADAMS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **59**, 5080, 5181; M. Z. NAKAMURA and J. MARILYN, *Proc. Mont. Acad. Sci.*, 1968, **28**, 51 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **71**, 1073); M. L. KHUBCHANDANI and S. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1987, **56**, 264.
2. S. P. SINGH, A. CHAUDHARI, V. I. STENOBERG and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **65**, 1678; A. K. BHAT, R. P. BHAMARIA, R. A. BELLARE and DELIWALA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 397; T. ZSOLMIA, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1962, **11**, 271 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **57**, 6431).
3. S. P. HIREMATH, K. M. K. SWAMY and B. H. M. MRUTHYUNJAYASWAMY, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1992, **2**, 119.
4. F. KAVANGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.
5. S. K. KULKARNI, "Hand Book of Experimental Pharmacology", Vallabha Prakashan, Delhi, 1987.
6. V. J. RAM and H. N. PANDEY, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1977, **41**, 137; *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1973, **86**, 575.

